

Adaptive iSCAT inference

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About:

A tweet about an idea regarding inferring information from an iSCAT measurement. Imagine a scattering sample in one arm of an interferometer, just like in [1,2]. In the other arm we position a spatial light modulator (SLM) with which we can control the light's amplitude and phase. The idea is now to fully cancel the field distribution of the "sample arm", which consists of a reference + scattered field just like in iSCAT. Hence we need to use the SLM to adaptively infer information about the scattered field by nulling the total field the interferometer's output:

$$E_{\text{reference}} + E_{\text{scattered}} + E_{\text{nulling}} = 0$$

Once we achieved that, we can increase the illumination so that we measure more scattered light. This only works until detector saturation is reached, from that point on we start to adaptively cancel the total field again. Meaning that we can increase illumination again, drastically increasing the scatter light contribution and hence SNR!

Tweet:

Tweet 1:

.@AndrewGYork asked a question about inference in phase contrast microscopy; I think iSCAT and MINFLUX are actually the same inference problem with different cost functions. But each cost function gives a completely different optimal strategy!

cc @balzarottifran, @philippkukura

Figure 1: Visualization of nulling scheme of [1,2] and Minflux inference.

[1] Andrew G. York, & Sanjay R. Varma. (2018, October 15). AndrewGYork/adaptive_interference_inference: Pre-print (Version v0.0.0). Zenodo. <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.1463274>

[2] Heintzmann, Rainer, & Becker, Jan. (2020, January 28). Measuring by Darkness? Let there be light! (Version v0.1). Zenodo. <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3629784>

Tweet 2:

Phase contrast → Cost function: photon dose to sample → ~2x better SNR than darkfield

MINIFLUX → Cost function: photon dose to fluorophore → ∞ better SNR than widefield

But what about iSCAT, where detected photons are free until the detector saturates (or the sample burns)?

Tweet 3:

iSCAT tries to maximize the scattered field without detector saturation. What if we made an SLM/interferometer-based iSCAT to null the total field?

We can increase illumination (and therefore SNR) much more, switching from detector-saturation-limited to sample damage-limited.

Figure 2: Mach-Zender interferometer with sample in one arm creating reference and scattered field (like in iSCAT) and a spatial light modulator in the second arm. With latter we try to adaptively infer information on the sample by canceling the total field at the interferometer's output port.

Tweet 4:

In case you haven't followed Andrew's initial post, addressing an interesting issue of "adaptive interference inference":

<https://twitter.com/AndrewGYork/status/1052664890718994432>

Tweet 5:

[1] Andrew G. York, & Sanjay R. Varma. (2018, October 15). AndrewGYork/adaptive_interference_inference: Pre-print (Version v0.0.0). Zenodo. <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.1463274>

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Here's my answer to Andrew's question, but I'm starting to think that nearby questions are even more interesting!

<https://twitter.com/RunningPhoton/status/1230935151493992449>

Tweet 6:

I think this is a fun family of questions, and I want to start a discussion about this. Anybody interested? Please invite others who might enjoy this!

[@markkitti](#) [@heintzmannlab](#) [@optrickster](#) [@sjoerdstallinga](#) [@JoergEnderlein](#) [@sandoghdarlab](#)
[@jamesdmanton](#) [@HenriquesLab](#) [@RetoPaul](#)

Tweet 7:

In case Twitter ceases to exist, here's a DOI: doi.org/ZENODOGOESHERE

[1] Andrew G. York, & Sanjay R. Varma. (2018, October 15). AndrewGYork/adaptive_interference_inference: Pre-print (Version v0.0.0). Zenodo. <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.1463274>

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